

IV IBEROAMERICAN CONFERENCE ON ADVANCED OXIDATION TECHNOLOGIES

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

This is to certify that **Leandro Oscar Conte** participated with the Oral presentation entitled *Abatement of paracetamol by ferrioxalate-mediated Fenton and photo-Fenton processes at near neutral pH: optimization by response surface methodology and toxicity evaluation*

(L. Conte, A. Schenone, B. Giménez, O. Alfano).

in the IV Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies held in Natal, Brazil
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Kind regards,

Professor Dr. Carlos Alberto Martínez-Huitle
General Chair, Organizing Committee
IV CIPOA in Natal, Brazil

Abatement of paracetamol by ferrioxalate-mediated Fenton and photo-Fenton processes at near neutral pH: optimization by response surface methodology and toxicity evaluationORAL
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This study discusses the degradation of paracetamol (PCT) by Fenton and photo-Fenton reactions at circumneutral pH with the aid of ferrioxalate and a solar simulator. A D-optimal design was applied in order to simultaneously evaluate the effect of three parameters: H₂O₂ concentration (*HP*), temperature (*T*) and radiation level (*Rad*) on PCT conversion. Once the set of 19 experiments was performed, the model was analysed by means of the analysis of variance. The largest effect was due to *Rad*, followed by *T* and finally the *HP* term. The found optimal conditions for each radiation level (No Rad, Low and High Rad) were tested and the obtained PCT conversions after 90 min of reaction (75.52%, 96.88% and 91.5%, respectively) were very close to those predicted by the models (71.28%, 96.75% and 92.75%, respectively). The acute toxicity (Microtox®) was only possible to completely remove after 240 min of reaction when high levels of radiation were applied.

Introduction

Paracetamol (PCT) is classified as an anti-inflammatory and non-steroidal analgesic and is one of the pharmaceutical products considered as emerging contaminant. Fenton and photo-Fenton processes have been applied to degrade PCT, giving different degradation efficiencies [1,2]. An interesting and potentially useful modification of Fenton and photo-Fenton reactions is the use of iron complexes (e.g. ferrioxalate) as catalyst source, which allow operating the system at pH conditions close to neutrality [3,4]

The study of the degradation of an organic compound through Fenton and photo-Fenton processes involves the evaluation of many factors. The present work proposes the application of a D-optimal design combined with response surface methodology (RSM) to evaluate and optimized three important parameters: temperature (*T*), oxidizing agent concentration (*HP*) and radiation level (*Rad*), on the PCT conversion.

Material and Methods

The experiments were carried out in a flat plate reactor of borosilicate glass (0.07 L). In the case of photo-Fenton reactions, the system was irradiated by a solar simulator (Oriel, model 9600). The storage tank (3 L) was equipped with a pH-meter, a thermometer and a liquid sample valve. The device was completed with a thermostatic bath and a centrifugal pump [5].

The conditions of operation were: initial PCT and Fe³⁺ concentrations 40 mg L⁻¹ and 3 mg L⁻¹ (molar ratio Fe/Ox=1/10), respectively, and pH=5.5 in the total of the experiments.

The key process parameters studied were: *T*, between 25 and 50 °C; *HP* concentration, between

189 and 756 mg L⁻¹ and *Rad* level, 0, 31.6 and 57.5 W m⁻². The experimental design matrix obtained by D-optimal consisted in a total of 19 experiment. The PCT conversion at 90 min of reaction was selected as the response under evaluation. D-optimal design was selected due to its versatility to analyse categorical factors (*Rad* in this study).

The acute toxicity was monitored during the reaction process. For this purpose, the inhibition of the luminescence of the photo-bacteria strain *Vibrio fischeri* NRRL-B-11177 was measured after 15 min of incubation (Microtox Model 500, Toxicity Analyser).

Results and Discussion

RSM was performed in order to statistically evaluate the degradation of PCT by a D-optimal design.

PCT conversions after 90 min were fitted to a polynomial model. Multiple regression analysis was used to calculate the model coefficients and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) with 95% confidence level to validate them, resulting in the following expression:

$$X_{90}^{PCT} (\%) = 75.24 + 16.02X_1 - 2.16X_2 - 36.73X_3 [1] \quad \text{Eq.(1)}$$
$$+ 17.71X_2 [2] + 18.47X_3 [1] - 10.58X_3 [2]$$
$$- 0.35X_2 X_3 [1] - 1.60X_2 X_3 [2] - 2.15X_1^2 - 3.25X_2^2$$

Where *X*₁, *X*₂ and *X*₃ represent the coded values of the variable's parameters in the model (*T*, *HP* and *Rad*, respectively). All the terms were significant (*p* < 0.05), except *X*₁*X*₂ term which was not considered due to its high *p* value.

Satisfactory values of standard deviation (0.74), *R*² and adjusted *R*² (0.9997 and 0.9993, respectively) were obtained for the model.

The interaction plot between T and Rad is presented in Fig.1, for the lowest HP concentration. As can be seen, increasing the T (from 25 to 50 °C), a larger amplitude of PCT conversion was obtained (difference of 69.69% in the observed X_{PCT}^{90} (%)) for dark conditions in comparison with the produced effect when the system is irradiated (difference of 10.87% in the observed X_{PCT}^{90} (%)). Similar behaviour was observed for high radiation condition.

Figure 1. Interaction plot between T and Rad . Experimental (symbols) and predicted (continuous line) results for a fixed HP concentration ($HP=189$ ppm).

Eqs. 2 to 4 represent the RSM models in actual terms that describe the PCT conversion for each Rad level (M1: Dark, M2: Low Rad, M3: High Rad).

$$M1: X_{90}^{PCT}(\%) = -91.333 + 3.912T + 0.031HP - 0.015T^2 - 4.162 \times 10^{-5}HP^2 \quad \text{Eq.(2)}$$

$$M2: X_{90}^{PCT}(\%) = 51.926 + 1.601T + 0.026HP - 0.015T^2 - 4.162 \times 10^{-5}HP^2 \quad \text{Eq.(3)}$$

$$M3: X_{90}^{PCT}(\%) = 38.420 + 1.843T + 0.037HP - 0.015T^2 - 4.162 \times 10^{-5}HP^2 \quad \text{Eq.(4)}$$

From these equations, it can be observed that larger T and HP values (terms with positive sign) would result in a higher PCT conversions. On the other hand, the influence of the HP^2 term is negative since an excess of H_2O_2 produces a hydroxyl radical scavenging effect and accelerates its self-decomposition. A negative effect is also expected at high operating temperatures (negative sign of the term T^2) since iron complex could decompose, with the consequent catalyst precipitation.

The response surfaces or each model (M1, M2 and M3) are presented in Figure 2. For all the range of T and HP concentrations evaluated, the lowest PCT conversions were reached for the dark system (Figure 2a). Being the minimum value the one reached using the lowest T and HP concentration (X_{PCT}^{90} (%) = 1.15%).

Figure 2. Response surfaces for PCT conversions after 90 min versus T and HP . (a) M1, (b) M2 and (c) M3.

The significant influence of the T in the Fenton process can be confirmed since in this dark condition and $HP=472$ ppm, the X_{PCT}^{90} (%) increased 37.5 times by using a higher operating T (50 °C vs. 25 °C). On the other hand, it is necessary to highlight the important effect of radiation on the system. For all irradiated conditions, X_{PCT}^{90} (%) were higher than 77% (Figures 2b and c). Moreover, PCT conversions close to 100% were observed using high radiation levels ($Rad = 57.5$ W m⁻²).

From the developed mathematical models (Eqs. 2 to 4), the optimal operating conditions were estimated to maximize the pollutant conversion, considering the minimum HP dose. That is: $T=50^\circ\text{C}$ and $HP=326.3$ ppm (dark condition), $T=50^\circ\text{C}$ and $HP=189$ ppm (low Rad), and $T=40^\circ\text{C}$ and $HP=189$

ppm (high Rad). It should be noted that the predicted optimum conversions (71.28%, 96.75% and 92.75%, respectively) were close to those observed experimentally (75.52%, 96.88% and 91.50%, respectively).

Furthermore, the evolution of the toxicity in the system (expressed as percentage of inhibition of bioluminescence of *V. fischeri* bacteria strains after 15 min of incubation, $I(\%)$) was monitored in the experiments under optimal conditions. Table 1 presents the obtained $I(\%)$ together with PCT relative concentration in the case of high radiation. The relative concentration (with respect to the initial PCT concentration) of the main reactions products

(hydroquinone and 1,4-benzoquinone) are also shown.

First, it can be observed that the maximum and minimum levels of toxicity found in the system were closely related to the maximum and minimum concentrations observed for the HQ and BQ. A reduction in the toxicity of the system was achieved as the reaction progresses. Similar behaviour was observed in the experiments under dark and low radiation. However, only by operating the system with high levels of radiation it was possible to completely remove the toxicity of the system ($I(\%) = 0$) after 240 min of reaction.

Table 1. Experimental relative concentrations vs. time for PCT, HQ, BQ and $I(\%)$ at the optimum conditions for high radiation (57.5 W m^{-2})^a

Time (min)	PCT	HQ	BQ	$I(\%)$
0	1.00	0.00	0.00	0
15	0.63	0.03	0.01	69
30	0.27	0.11	0.02	91
60	0.09	0.09	0.00	78
90	0.03	0.05	0.00	52
120	0.02	0.03	0.00	36
180	0.00	0.00	0.00	18
240	0.00	0.00	0.00	0

^a HQ: hydroquinone. BQ: 1,4-benzoquinone.

Conclusions

Paracetamol could be successfully degraded under Fenton and photo-Fenton conditions at pH=5.5 using ferrioxalate as iron source. In order to study the effects of the process parameters: HP , T and Rad , a D-optimal experimental design combined with response surface methodology was applied. Among the studied variables, it could be seen that the largest effect in PCT conversion was due to Rad (the most significant term), followed by T and finally the HP term.

The conversion achieved by the Fenton process at the optimal conditions ($X_{PCT}^{90}(\%)=75.52\%$) was lower than those obtained with low ($X_{PCT}^{90}(\%)=96.88\%$) and high ($X_{PCT}^{90}(\%)=91.5\%$) Rad levels. Moreover, the obtained results are very close to the values predicted by the models (71.28%, 96.75% and 92.75%, respectively). Under this optimum conditions, the $I(\%)$ was evaluated. Although PCT conversions close to 100% are reached after 180 min of reaction, longer reaction times are necessary to achieve a complete removal of the toxicity in the system (only for high Rad conditions). This was associated with the presence of highly toxic reaction intermediates (hydroquinone and 1,4-benzoquinone).

Acknowledgments

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This is to certify that **Leandro Oscar Conte** participated with the Oral presentation entitled *Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of Paracetamol under natural pH conditions using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source. A theoretical and experimental study.*

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Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of Paracetamol under natural pH conditions using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source. A theoretical and experimental study.

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A theoretical and experimental study of the Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of Paracetamol (PCT) is presented. A kinetic model derived from a reaction sequence is proposed using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source and a solar simulator, for conditions of pH close to neutrality. Operating the system with high radiation level (solar simulator) and the highest concentration of hydrogen peroxide (HP), the conversion of PCT after 180 min of reaction was close to 100% over the full range of working temperatures. However, complete destruction of the main intermediaries, HQ and BQ (hydroquinone and 1,4-benzoquinone) was obtained only when high levels of radiation were applied at 240 min of reaction. A good correlation was obtained between the experimental data and the results obtained with the model. The root mean square error (RMSE) for PCT, HP, Oxa, HQ and BQ concentrations were 3.62×10^{-2} mM, 7.65×10^{-1} mM, 4.85×10^{-2} mM, 3.25×10^{-1} mM and 2.4 mM, respectively.

Introduction

Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) have demonstrated to efficiently degrade several persistent compounds. Among them, the Fenton and photo-Fenton processes have been widely used for the treatment of contaminants present in water. An interesting and potentially useful modification is the use of iron complexes as catalyst source which allow operating the system at a wide range of pH conditions close to neutrality. In addition, it greatly improves the photocatalytic activity of the systems [1,2].

The present study aims at developing a kinetic model that can describe the Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of Paracetamol (PCT) at pH=5.5 in a flat plate reactor irradiated with a solar simulator. PCT was selected as model contaminant being a widely used antipyretic and analgesic. Although it is degraded quite effectively by biological processes, appreciable concentrations of this drug were detected in real industrial wastewater (between 5.6 and 294 mg L⁻¹) [3,4].

Material and Methods

Kinetic experiments were performed in a lab-scale flat plate reactor of borosilicate glass with external recycle. The storage tank includes a pH-meter, a thermometer and a liquid sample valve. A thermostatic bath was used to ensure constant temperature during the reaction and a centrifugal pump to achieve a high recirculation flow rate and good mixing conditions. The total volume of the treated solution was 3.0 L, while the reactor irradiated volume was 0.07 L [5]. A solar simulator (Oriol, model 9600) was used as the irradiation

source.

Experimental runs were defined by a D-optimal design. The effect of the variables: HP concentration (between 189 and 756 mg L⁻¹), temperature (between 25 and 50 °C) and level of radiation (0, 31.6 and 57.5 W m⁻²) on PCT degradation was assessed. Thus, 19 experiments were performed. For all tests, pH was 5.5, the PCT concentration was 40 mg L⁻¹, Fe³⁺ concentration was set at 3 mg L⁻¹ and oxalate (Oxa) concentration was 47.5 mg L⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

The main reactions involved in the system are summarized in Table 1 (Reaction N0 to N7). The degradation rate expressions of PCT, HP, Oxa, HQ and BQ, can be written by using the matrix representation as indicated in eq. 1 [1]. For the kinetic studies performed in the lab-scale flat plate reactor, the mass balances and the initial conditions are given by the set of first order, ordinary differential eqs. 2 and 3 (matrix notation). The kinetic parameters were estimated from experimental and kinetic model results by applying the nonlinear regression procedure of Newton Gauss-Marquardt (Table 1).

$$\mathbf{R}(x,t) = \mathbf{R}^T(t) + \mathbf{R}^{Irr}(x,t) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{C}(t) = \mathbf{R}^T(t) + \varphi \left(\sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^{\alpha}(\underline{x}, t) \right)_{V_{IRR}} \mathbf{\Gamma}(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}^0 \quad t = 0 \quad (3)$$

Equation 1 is solved to obtain the mathematical expressions of $R_i(x,t)$. To do this, the steady state approximation (SSA) may be applied for highly reactive radicals (OH^*). In addition, only the reaction constants ($k^{**}_1, k^{**}_4, k^{**}_5$ and k^{**}_6) and the $\varphi^{**}_{c_2O_4^{2-}}$ quantum yield were estimated and optimized. The others kinetic parameters were taken from a previous work [1].

The first term on the right-hand side of eqs.1 or 2 corresponds to the thermal reaction rate that gives the i -component degradation by the Fenton reaction taking place in the non-irradiated liquid volume. On the other hand, the second term on the right-hand side of these equations corresponds to the i -component degradation by both, the radiation activated and thermal reactions occurring inside the irradiated liquid volume (photo-Fenton reaction).

For the numerical evaluation of the photo-Fenton term, it is necessary to know the value of the Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption (LVRPA) at every point inside the reactor and then to compute the LVRPA averaged over the reactor volume. This is $\langle \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(x,t) \rangle_{V_{IRR}}$. To compute it, a one-dimensional radiation field model was used [6]. Thus,

$$e_{\lambda}^a(x,t) = \kappa_{\lambda}(x,t) q_{w,\lambda} f_{\lambda} \exp[-\kappa_{T,\lambda}(x,t)x] \quad (4)$$

where $q_{w,\lambda}$ is the spectral net radiation flux at the reactor wall, f_{λ} the normalized spectral distribution of the lamp output power, $\kappa_{\lambda}(x,t)$ the volumetric absorption coefficient of the reacting species, and $\kappa_{T,\lambda}(x,t)$ the volumetric absorption coefficient of the medium. More details on the LVRPA calculation can be found elsewhere [5].

Figure 1 shows experimental data and kinetic model predictions (relative concentrations) of PCT, HQ, BQ, HP and Oxa evaluated for low and high radiation levels. Even though, in both operating conditions (Fig. 1a and 1b), the complete conversion of PCT (X_{PCT}) is achieved after 120 min of reaction (non-detectable concentrations), the test using low radiation needed a higher reaction temperature and a dosage of oxidizing agent 4 times higher. Moreover, for the all range of T and HP used, the conversions obtained in dark conditions were always lower than those achieved under irradiated ones. Being the minimum value the one reached using the lowest T and HP concentration ($X_{PCT}^{180 \text{ min}} = 49.5\%$, $T = 25 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $HP = 189 \text{ ppm}$). Only using high reaction T, significant conversions of PCT were achieved ($X_{PCT}^{180 \text{ min}} = 94.5\%$, for $T=50^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $HP=334 \text{ ppm}$). Therefore, it is necessary to highlight the beneficial effect of the radiation and T in the process.

(b) Figure 1. Model and experimental results for PCT, HP, Oxa, HQ and BQ in relative concentrations for pH=5.5. **(a)** Low Rad, $T=50^{\circ}\text{C}$, $HP=756 \text{ ppm}$; **(b)** High Rad, $T=40^{\circ}\text{C}$, $HP=189 \text{ ppm}$. Keys: (continuous line) model result. (\blacklozenge)PCT, (\blacksquare) HP, (\blacktriangle) Oxa, (\times) HQ, and (\bullet) BQ.

Predicted and experimental results for Fenton and photo-Fenton reactions are also represented in Figure 2. It shows a 3-D plot of $X_{PCT}^{90 \text{ min}}$ as a function of T and HP concentration, for low and high radiation levels. For all T and HP conditions, $X_{PCT}^{90 \text{ min}}$ higher than 77% were obtained. However, as temperature is increased, these conversion reach values close to 100%.

Figure 2. Predicted (surfaces) and experimental (symbols) PCT conversions after 90 min vs. reaction temperatures and HP concentrations. Keys: high rad (diamonds) and low rad (squares).

In order to test the model reliability, the root mean square error (RMSE) was calculated. The proposed model showed a relatively good agreement with the experimental data, giving RMSE for PCT, HP, Oxa, HQ and BQ: 3.62×10^{-2} mM, 7.65×10^{-1} mM, 4.85×10^{-2} mM, 3.252×10^{-1} mM and 2.4 mM, respectively.

Table 1. Reaction scheme of PCT degradation

N	Reaction step	Estimated kinetic parameter
0	$Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} \xrightarrow{h\nu} Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + CO_2 + 1.5C_2O_4^{2-}$	$\varphi^*_{Fe^{II}(C_2O_4)} = 1.21 molEins^{-1}$ $\varphi^*_{C_2O_4^{2-}} = 0.50 molEins^{-1}$
1	$Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + 2C_2O_4^{2-} + OH^* + OH^-$	$k^{**}_1 = \exp \left[A^{**}_1 + B^{**}_1 \left(\frac{T - T_{ref}}{T} \right) \right]$ $A^{**}_1 = \ln(k_{\infty,1}) - \frac{E_1}{RT_{ref}} = -2.64 (-)$ $B^{**}_1 = \frac{E_1}{RT_{ref}} = 8.47 (-)$
2	$Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + H_2O_2 + 2C_2O_4^{2-} \rightarrow Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + OH^* + OH^-$	$k^*_2 = 3.10 \times 10^4 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
3	$H_2O_2 + OH^* \rightarrow O_2^* + H^*$	$k^*_3 = 3.76 \times 10^7 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
4	$PCT + OH^* \rightarrow HQ$	$k^{**}_4 = 1.3 \times 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
5	$HQ + OH^* \rightarrow BQ$	$k^{**}_5 = 5.90 \times 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
6	$BQ + OH^* \rightarrow products$	$k^{**}_6 = 5.00 \times 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
7	$C_2O_4^{2-} + OH^* \rightarrow 2CO_2 + OH^-$	$k^*_7 = 7.70 \times 10^6 M^{-1} s^{-1}$

* Values taken from Conte et al., 2016 [1].

** Estimated in this study (taking into account the values from specific literature as a range).

$T_{ref} = 298 \text{ }^\circ K$; R is the ideal gas constant, $8.31 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$

Conclusions

A theoretical and experimental study of the homogeneous Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of PCT is presented. A simplified kinetic model derived from a reaction sequence was proposed using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source for conditions of pH close to neutrality. A good agreement between kinetic model results and experimental data was observed.

Acknowledgments

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